

PHOENIX meets CO⁵BOLD: 3D NLTE radiative transfer calculations for M-dwarf chromospheres

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Abstract

M-dwarf atmospheres are phenomenologically so rich that it is currently impossible to include all the physical processes in one astrophysical simulation code. 1D models have greatly improved our understanding of the radiative properties of M-dwarf photospheres and important achievements have been obtained in 1D and 3D magneto-hydrodynamic simulations. Using a snapshot from a CO⁵BOLD M-dwarf simulation as input model, we use the 3D atmosphere code PHOENIX/3D to compute the radiative properties of a M-dwarf photosphere-chromosphere atmosphere with NLTE treatment for several atomic species and background atomic and molecular opacities.

1 Introduction

M-dwarfs are the largest fraction of stars in the Milky Way. Many exhibit low to strong activity, in the form of starspots, chromospheric/coronal emission and flares. They are characterised by low effective temperatures T_{eff} , from 2300 to 3900 K, and, therefore, represent challenging observational targets.

To fully understand the vast phenomenology that distinguishes these objects, we have to build models that take into account all these properties. Due to the low T_{eff} , a detailed treatment of atomic and molecular opacities is necessary to model the photosphere. At the same time, the chromosphere features warm, partially ionised, rarefied gas. Because of the low densities, the collisional rates cannot balance the non-Planckian radiative rates. Consequently, the assumption of local thermal equilibrium (LTE) is too simplistic (Hauschildt *et al.*, 1996). 3D magneto-hydrodynamics (MHD) frameworks must be used to deal with convection, magnetic activity and plasma dynamics. Unfortunately, with the current technological capabilities, we cannot run a single astrophysical simulation code that combines all these requirements.

Several studies have been conducted recently to investigate in detail the hydrodynamic properties of M-dwarf atmospheres. Ludwig *et al.* (2002, 2006) investigated in detail the stellar granulation and convective flows. Their 3D simulations included a radiative transfer treatment using the Opacity Binning Method (Nordlund, 1982): shortly, frequencies, from continua and lines, that reach optical depth unity within a certain depth range, are combined into one frequency bin. This technique is a great improvement over simple assumptions like grey opacity and, currently, a good compromise for 3D MHD simulations that, due to the current technological limitations, cannot treat a fully frequency dependent radiation field.

Wedemeyer *et al.* (2013) extended the simulations conducted by Ludwig *et al.* to include magnetic fields, using the CO⁵BOLD code (Freytag *et al.*, 2012). They simulated an

AD Leo-like atmosphere composed by the top of the convection zone, the photosphere and the highly dynamic chromosphere. Here we present our results from 3D NLTE radiative transfer calculations with PHOENIX/3D (Hauschildt & Baron (2014) and previous papers in the series) using a snapshot from the grid of M-dwarf atmosphere models by Wedemeyer *et al.* (2013).

2 Computational framework

We use a snapshot, i.e. a single time-step, from a M-dwarf simulation by Wedemeyer *et al.* (2013) with $T_{\text{eff}} = 3240$ K, $\log g = 4.5$, and a vertical initial magnetic field of strength $B_{z,0} = 10$ G (the smallest initial B from the series of models in Wedemeyer *et al.* (2013)). The original Cartesian grid of the model counts $120 \times 120 \times 261$ cells, with an extension of $1950 \times 1950 \times 1692$ km. The vertical axis goes from -713 km below the $\bar{\tau}_{\text{R}} = 1$ (mean Rosseland opacity) surface, i.e. “the bottom of the photosphere”, to +979 km in the chromosphere. The model presented here was spatially binned to $33 \times 33 \times 257$ cells in order to decrease the computational cost of the calculations. The gas properties span a wide range in temperature, pressure and density. The lower regions of the binned model correspond to the low photosphere and the correspondent temperature maps (Fig. 1a) exhibit the granulation pattern due to convection. The upper layers (Fig. 1b) show a non-uniform/filamentary structure, with strong differences in temperature from cell to cell. In these layers, the hotter regions are related to shock-fronts and the colder regions to post-shocked, cooled gas, respectively. Fig. 1c displays a slice through the model that clearly shows the coexistence of cold and hot gas at different heights in the atmosphere. Our radiative transfer calculations with PHOENIX/3D included the following species with NLTE treatment: H I, He I, and C, N, O, Ca, Mg with ionisation stages I and II. The total number of NLTE levels is 1 632, corresponding to 18 580 transitions, with a wavelength grid of $\sim 180\,000$ points. Atomic and molecular background (LTE)

lines are also considered. We apply periodic boundary conditions on the x and y faces, diffusion condition at the bottom boundary, and $I^- = 0$ at the top boundary.

3 Results

The spectrum (Figs. 2) is computed from the average, across the xy -plane, for the outermost layer, of the outgoing component of the flux. The spectrum below 3000 Å (Fig. 2a) is dominated by a weak continuum and features a forest of emission lines, many characterised by an absorption core. In the optical range (Fig. 2b), the spectrum is dominated by the molecular bands typical of M-dwarf photospheres. No emission lines are present. The IR spectrum (Fig. 2c) also resembles a “photosphere” spectrum for a M-dwarf. For each wavelength point in the spectrum, we can plot a colour coded image of the outgoing flux at the outermost layer, i.e. the flux that emerges from the top boundary. Comparing these flux images with the gas temperature maps at different heights in the input model gives a first idea about the formation height of lines and continua. In the core of strong UV lines, like Lyman- α and Mg II (3a and 3b respectively), the flux maps resemble the temperature maps at high layers in the model grid, correspondent to chromospheric heights. The Ca II 8544 Å line core flux map (Fig. 3c) shows a more complex structure, that samples different layers in the atmosphere. In contrast, in the line wing (Fig. 3d), we can clearly recognise the granulation pattern observed at the $\tau_R = 1$ surface (Fig. 1a); the infrared continuum at 10 μm (Fig. 2c) shows a similar appearance. The continuum at 0.1 mm (Fig. 3f) displays the granulation pattern as well but more structures are visible, originating from higher layers.

We can compute synthetic images of the model, at any wavelength point, for any desired direction, specified by the angles θ (the angle between observer and normal to the surface) and ϕ (the polar angle). Figs. 4a, 4b, and 4c show the intensity maps for the outermost layer, at 5000 Å (optical continuum), for three progressively higher inclinations. The limb-darkening is evident when observing at higher θ .

Thanks to the NLTE treatment for the species mentioned above, we compute, for each ion, the departure coefficients b_i for each state included. In Fig. 5 we present the departure coefficients for the ground state of three different species, i.e. H I, He I, and O II, in the same vertical slice used for Fig. 1c. We only show the heights above 0 km, because the $b_i = 1$ (indicating LTE) everywhere in the layers below. The b_i 's map for the H I ground state (Fig. 5a) shows how strong the departure from LTE is and how it matches the temperature structure of the higher layers. The lowest values for the H I departure coefficients are several orders of magnitude higher compared to other species, like He I and O II (Figs. 5b and 5c respectively). The departure coefficients are below unity when going upwards in the atmosphere. Because of the low density, the level populations are basically set by the radiative rates only. With the gas temperature decreasing (on average) going upwards, the atoms “see” a radiation field, coming from the bottom, hotter than the one that would be set in LTE conditions. As a result, upward transitions are more likely, resulting in under-populated levels, and therefore low departure coefficients. Due to the shocks, the temperature may increase greatly from voxel to voxel. Where the gas temperature is high, the b_i 's take values above unity. This is due to the atoms experiencing a radiative tempera-

ture lower than the gas temperature. The levels are therefore over-populated in comparison with LTE conditions and the departure coefficients increase. At the shock fronts, where the temperature gradient changes sign, the b_i 's take extreme values. The cold gas is irradiated by the photons originating from the shock fronts (through radiative de-excitation of the aforementioned over-populated levels), and, for the same mechanism described above, the b_i 's decrease. This is a clear example demonstrating that LTE assumptions fail outside of the photosphere. We can “witness” this process by comparing Fig. 1c with Figs. 5 at coordinates $x \sim 1000$ km and $z \sim +700$ km. For He I, b_i 's take lower values because of the higher excitation energies required, while over-ionisation is responsible for the even lower departure coefficients for O II.

Number densities for each atomic and molecular species considered are also computed. PHOENIX/3D equation of state solver ACES (Astrophysical Chemical Equilibrium Solver-Equations of State) is based on the VCS method (Villars-Cruise-Smith (Smith & Missen, 1982)): it computes the ideal gas stoichiometric equilibrium, taking elements abundances, temperature, and pressure as inputs. The example presented in Fig. 6 shows a colour map of the number density for CO, one the most optically thick molecule that contains most of the carbon in the photosphere. The molecule concentration is tightly related to the temperature, showing large variations from voxel to voxel when crossing shock fronts.

4 Outlook

We are currently computing more models using different input structures from the CO⁵BOLD grid, also less “expensive” models, in terms of memory and CPU time, by decreasing the number of levels and transitions in the NLTE treatment. Using a similar approach, we are also working on solar photosphere-chromosphere models.

As mentioned above, M-dwarf atmospheres represent particularly challenging environments to model, due to the large number of atomic (and perhaps also molecular) species demanding NLTE treatment, and the presence of an active, dynamic chromosphere. The simulations presented here show that it is currently possible, when using large supercomputers, to compute complex 3D NLTE static models with the same micro-physics treatment of 1D models. In the context of chromospheric physics, these models can help us investigating the importance of the 3D geometry against the classical 1D approach, and, with further development of the code and future computational facilities, we could finally consistently solve the multi-dimensional R-MHD problem.

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Figure 1: Temperature in the binned CO⁵BOLD model used as input atmosphere for our simulation. Please note that the original model atmospheres have a four times higher grid resolution.

Figure 2: Horizontally averaged flux spectra for a) UV, b) optical, and c) IR wavelengths.

Figure 3: Color maps for the outgoing flux at the outermost layer for different wavelength points.

Figure 4: Intensity images at 5000 Å images for viewing angles. The colorbar range is set according to the lowest and highest value of the intensity at all angles.

Figure 5: Departure coefficients for the ground state of selected atomic species. White indicates $b_i = 1$, i.e. LTE conditions.

Figure 6: Number density for CO. The hot shock fronts in the chromosphere lead to dissociation of CO and thus lower CO densities, which are visible as red filaments along the shock fronts.

M-type Dwarf Stars and the Influence on Habitable Extra-solar Planets”.

References

- Freytag, B., Steffen, M., Ludwig, H.-G., Wedemeyer-Böhm, S., Schaffenberger, W., *et al.* 2012, *Journal of Computational Physics*, 231, 919.
- Hauschildt, P. H., Allard, F., Alexander, D. R., Schweitzer, A., & Baron, F. 1996, In *Stellar Surface Structure*, edited by K. G. Strassmeier & J. L. Linsky, *IAU Symposium*, vol. 176, p. 539.
- Hauschildt, P. H. & Baron, E. 2014, *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 566, A89.
- Ludwig, H.-G., Allard, F., & Hauschildt, P. H. 2002, *A&A*, 395, 99.
- Ludwig, H.-G., Allard, F., & Hauschildt, P. H. 2006, *A&A*, 459, 599.
- Nordlund, A. 1982, *A&A*, 107, 1.
- Smith, W. R. & Missen, R. W. 1982, *Chemical reaction equilibrium analysis: theory and algorithms*. Wiley series in chemical engineering (Wiley). ISBN 9780471093473.
- Wedemeyer, S., Ludwig, H.-G., & Steiner, O. 2013, *Astronomische Nachrichten*, 334, 137.